

BIO-MOLECULES THROUGH HOLOGRAPHY OPTICAL TWEEZERS

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ABSTRACT:

We study neutrino-like photons or quanta as light rays of incoming information, created by the forces of new energies of SU(6), SU(12), SU(24),....etc. appearing with different gradients forces with multiple foci behaving like as laser beams of holographic optical tweezers(HOT), optimising or controlling the potentiality, the multiple trapping of nano-particles then fabricated colloidal lithography. We assumed these kind new light rays, not only trapping the single colloidal particles but also construct the dynamical status of single strand DNA, single proteins etc. and encapsulated all the up-converting quantum nano-particles from exotic fluid controlling all other resonating vibration “modes”, for fabricating the structure of different complex bio-molecules like ssDNA, Single Protein, then Protein chain formations with monomers, polymers etc. Then, increasing the known ordinary matter atomic structures by increasing the atomic numbers for constructing different stable or unstable elements, bio-cells or bonding between charge chemical elements or compound elements having different bonding angles etc., each performance through chemical reaction would be possible when supplying the aforesaid new energies from another phases.

Keywords: SUT (Super Unified Gaussian Theory), New energy source SU(6); New bosons namely J_k & J_{k3} .

J_{k8} , J_{k15} , J_{k24} , J_{k35} .

Introduction:

We assumed that our Physical Universe appeared through a dynamical symmetry breaking system of Generalised Gaussian Energy Group (GGEG), can be expressed mathematically are as follows:

$SU(5) \supset SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)$; $SU(11) \supset SU(6) \times SU(5) \times U(1)$; $SU(23) \supset SU(12) \times SU(11) \times U(1)$; $SU(47) \supset SU(24) \times SU(23) \times U(1)$;.....so on. Thus we have, $SU(12n-1) \supset SU(6n) \times SU(6n-1) \times U(1)$, where, $n = 2^0, 2^1, 2^2, 2^3, 2^4, \dots, \infty$ i.e. $SU(12n-1) \supset SU(6n) \times \dots \times SU(24) \times SU(12) \times SU(6) \times SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)$.

Thus, our Universe actually filled with different densities of new energy sources created by different kind of bosons by their respective subgroups, which are always changes to one-another by exchanging the bosons of their respective unified groups randomly after symmetry breaking from Big-Rip singularity till to the symmetry breaking of SU(11) & SU(5). Considering it appears through different phases filling the infinite space-time as the phases like various densities of gaseous stages are mathematically as imaginary space-time (according to the Einstein's GRT that real time can't defined outside the gravitating sphere, again space is function of time, so outside the gravitating sphere, we can assume the space-time is mathematically then imaginary) other than the appearance of matter phase appeared by SUT of SU(11) (like it is vapour state) & by GUT of SU(5) (like as liquid or solid state). Ultimately, we found our physical or matter universe appeared by the symmetry breaking of the “Super Unified Gaussian Energy Group SU(11)” with 10-dimensional space-times then our 4-dimensional Einstein's matter universe. Thus we need a Revised Standard Model of Physics or an extension of the Standard Model of Physics.

In recent years, we observed that optical tweezers have emerged as a leading technique in the field of biophysics, due to their ability to detect and to constrain the position of micrometer-sized objects in three dimensions and exert biologically relevant pico-Newton forces. Compare this by experimentally implementation technique of optical tweezers with the early stages for natural development of the biophysics to our physical universe. Optical tweezers have found a particularly fruitful application to the single-molecule studies, where tethering macromolecules to optically trapped beads has enabled measurements of their response to extension and force, revealing, *e.g.*, mechanical response properties of DNA and free energy

surfaces for nucleic acid and protein unfolding. Extending the manipulation and force measurement capabilities of optical tweezers to the mechanical probing of higher-order biological structures, such as cells and soft biomaterials, requires the ability to stretch these higher-dimensional structures in more than one direction.

Ordinary Matter Particle Formations:

According to the Einstein's GRT or Big-Bang theory that our physical or matter universe expanded with unfolding the folding universe like an expansion of a balloon due to the dark energies or dark matters changes to ordinary matters. Considering, here the master mind as the photon-likes quanta of neutrinos of the aforesaid new the energies as light rays of laser-like beams passing through the aperture or nano-hole of that balloon-like closed universe for expanding the matter universe then everything within the closed universe. I think there possibilities of relatively double nano-holes (although, any kind of empty or vacuum spaces are always filling with different kind of new energies belonging to another phases explained before in my articles) or multiple nano-holes or maybe black-holes instead of single hole for creating holographic optical tweezers within the closed physical universe for trapping newly created of colloidal particles or up-converting masses of nano-particles of the Brownian motions within resonant vibrations exerted from exotic matter fluids then fabricating the structures of everything of this matter universe including live matters. Killing with real time there increasing expansion rate of the physical universe while decreasing after certain time with properly maintaining the thermodynamic laws of fluid characters. We then find the appearances of different dynamic vortices for creating galaxies then clusters etc. within the ocean of fluid universe.

So, therefore it is to be consider that in the early stages or thereafter of our unfolding physical matter universe, there may be possible to creates DNH or multiple nano-holes for optically trapping nascent nano-particles in natural way after phase transition and done a crucial deterministic role of everything including lives through the incoming information of new light rays within our closed universe. According to the aforesaid explanation where creating the variable wave frequencies packets by interacting with photons appeared through the incoming information of light rays of neutrino-likes of the new energy sources of SU(6), SU(12), SU(24),...etc. as are quanta-like in wave status within our closed physical universe i.e. find different incoming gradient forces of invisible tachyon particles with different signalling amplitudes then broadcasting through the designation of radio-waves. According to the inclination, it is measuring as laser-like holographic optical beams and hence found holographic optical tweezers (HOT) for trapping different nano-particles from colloidal fluid then fabricated the structures of DNA, Protein etc. by the modes of resonance vibrations after changing the exotic matter fluid.

It is remembering that if we advances towards the symmetry breaking of GUT of SU(5) i.e. $SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)$ from the symmetry breaking of SU(11), the strong strength of special force of SU(6) may have unchanged for (10-7)-dimensional due to flat universe and higher strengths(within 5th & 6th dimensional black-Hole stage within event horizon) than of matter forces of 4-dimensional closed universe created before and after the symmetry breaking of SU(5). Thus, strength of weak force of SU(2) decreases as the strength of strong force of SU(3) increases for constructing ordinary matter particles by quarks & gluons while the strength of SU(6) remain unchanged. Hence, all kind of matter particle formations is under the ruled of SU(6), that means any kind of assemble(synthesises or by chemical reactions) of its dynamical parts towards for achieving the completion of apparently closed body with or without sense are always requires the forces of SU(6) as the hidden background interactions. Thus, it is interesting that particle-likes with special kind of forces created by the energy group SU(6) together with tightly binding by the quark-types but lepton-likes are always latently interacted i.e. invisible from the sense of visible matter energy particles formations by quarks & gluons etc. Thus experimentally or physically observed matter particles accounted in the present physics forms by quarks & gluons etc., there ignored these hidden background interaction forces by energies of particle-likes with its forces. Hence therefore, it is very hard to construct artificially like as original DNA, Protein etc. only by accounting matter so called particles or not to the possible of all-round development without any credibility of the above stated new energy sources which are requires for the construction of any kind of material elements or taking a positive role for conducting chemical reactions, synthesises etc.

Hidden Forces in the Background of Matter Particle Interactions:

In the theory of $SU(11) \supset SU(6) \times SU(5) \times U(1)$, we have five neutral bosons $J_{k3}, J_{k8}, J_{k15}, J_{k24}, J_{k35}$ of $SU(6)$ corresponding the neutrino-likes are as $Z_{k3}^\circ, Z_{k8}^\circ, Z_{k15}^\circ, Z_{k24}^\circ, Z_{k35}^\circ$ [considering the notation are as usual like as Z° of the traditional weak neutrinos of the group $SU(2)$ of GUT model] with respect to the five diagonal matrices $I_3, I_8, I_{15}, I_{24}, I_{35}$ of $SU(6)$ having zero mass and without charge, just like as photon. However, the photon does not interact the neutrinos of $SU(2)$, while photon-likes by $J_{k3}, J_{k8}, J_{k15}, J_{k24}, J_{k35}$ does as because there is a basic difference between $SU(2)$ and $SU(6)$, having quark-types but lepton-likes. Photon-likes quanta as laser like light are accelerated by the strong strengths forces of neutrino-likes of $SU(6)$, hence there created a new kind of strong strengths forces, assuming as "Quantum Gravity" in the corresponding framework of $SU(6) \times U(1)$ which are therefore potentially very strong, that means providing forces by the interactions of $Z_{k3}^\circ, Z_{k8}^\circ, Z_{k15}^\circ, Z_{k24}^\circ, Z_{k35}^\circ$ and $W_1, W_2, W_4, W_5, W_6, \dots, W_{34}$, are very strong. The exchange any of $J_{k3}, J_{k8}, J_{k15}, J_{k24}, J_{k35}$ does not alter the status like as charges, although the new kind of strong interactions by $SU(6)$ does not directly involve with electric charges, but we can imagine it still seems like to demand the charge-like bosons by $J_{k1}, J_{k2}, J_{k4}, J_{k5}, J_{k6}, \dots, J_{k34}$ [like as between Z° & W_1^\pm in $SU(2)$] with respect to the non-diagonal matrices $I_1, I_2, I_4, I_5, I_6, \dots, I_{34}$ are permit an interchange or rearrange the wave functions between the charge-likes and neutrino-likes. Hence, this circumstances prompted efforts to link with one-way like a new kind of electromagnetic-type interaction, that means a new kind of pseudo-electro-strong interaction appears through the link $SU(6) \times U(1)$ i.e. brings the photon of $U(1)$ [the electrodynamics $U(1)$, which are inevitable arises particles that have the characteristics of a magnetic monopole. Monopoles are highly stable particles and once created they are not destructible and so they would survive as relics to the present epoch] which are therefore very closer to all bosons of $SU(6)$ and responsible for the creation of new kind of electromagnetic-type forces within the charge-like particles.

An analogy will illustrate the scenario that if we imagine an ordinary light of quanta are in wave of electromagnetic ocean and be quite successful at it, wouldn't be much of a stretch for us to image electrons as something like tethered buoys floating in an electromagnetic harbour. Along come the waves (new kind of light) by new energy sources as explained before which pull and tug at the buoys (electrons). Weak waves have no effects, but strong ones just might yank a buoy from their mooring and set it adrift. A wave model of light would predict an energy-amplitude relationship and not the energy-frequency relationship. Again, photoelectric experiments describe an electromagnetic ocean where monstrous swells wouldn't tip over a canoe, but tiny ripples would fling you into the air. If that wasn't enough, the photoelectrons seem to pop out from the surface of body too quickly. When light intensities are very low, the rate at which energy is delivered to the surface is downright sluggish. It should take a while for any one particular electron to capture enough of this diffuse energy to free itself. It should, but it doesn't.

Hence, light rays formed by the packets of photon-like neutrinos of new energies, excited electrons by flash-like cut-off as 0-1 binary-system of computer, depending on the flexibility of the impact surfaces then created photo-emissions or absorbed energy then creating variable photo currents of different amplitudes & intensities.

Conclusion:

Very recently, CERN of Geneva at LHC announced boldly that they were discovered more than 90 new particle-likes other than fundamental particles of block building like protons, neutrons, electrons etc. But those particles are only visible in the laboratory experiments and remains hidden in the background of ordinary particle interaction or block building particles, although scientist declared that those are formed by "charm quarks". Assuming that those are intermediate fundamental particles seems to be the auxiliary matter particles while there exists many more particle-likes explained in the SUT model of $SU(11)$ but importantly believe to be requires it for the formation and binding of all categories of ordinary matter elements. I believe to be possible in future to find more & more new particle-likes in the laboratory experiment with advancing our technology, which then confirm that, these are actual background for the causes of formation of the base elementary of bio molecules such as DNA, Protein molecules etc.

Relevant Image:

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